

Education Quarterly Reviews

Temel, A., & Mamak, H. (2023). Investigation of Secondary School Student's Value Perceptions and Attitudes Regarding to Physical Education and Sports Lesson. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 6(1), 133-151.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.06.01.693

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Investigation of Secondary School Student's Value Perceptions and Attitudes Regarding to Physical Education and Sports Lesson*

Ahmet Temel¹, Hüdaverdi Mamak²

¹ Eskil 75th Year Anatolian High School, T.R. Ministry of National Education, Aksaray, Turkey. ORCID: 0000-0001-9215-6106

² Faculty of Sports Sciences, Niğde Ömer Halisdemir University, Niğde, Turkey. ORCID: 0000-0002-0842-5949

Correspondence: Ahmet Temel, Eskil 75th Year Anatolian High School, T.R. Ministry of National Education, Aksaray, Turkey. Tel: 05375101551. E-mail: dr.ahmettemel@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aimed to examine the value perceptions and attitudes of secondary school students towards physical education and sports lessons. The research, which was designed in a quasi-experimental model with a pretest-posttest control group, was conducted with 91 7th-grade students in the second semester of the 2020-2021 academic year. The students were divided into 4 groups according to the course content applied in the physical education lesson: "Sports Education Model (SEM)", "Physical Activity Card (PAC)", "Traditional Children's Games (TCG)" and "Control Group (CG)". Physical education lessons were carried out with the groups for 10 weeks. The data were collected using the mixed method explanatory sequential design approach. "Physical Education and Sports Lesson Values Education Scale" and "Physical Education and Sports Attitude Scale" were used to collect quantitative data. In the analysis of the data, arithmetic means, correlation, Wilcoxon, Mann Whitney U, and Kruskal Wallis analyzes were performed. Qualitative data, on the other hand, were collected through lesson observations and focus group interviews and analyzed by content analysis. According to the research findings; there has been an increase in secondary school students' physical education lesson value perceptions and attitudes. The most developed value of the students was friendship, followed by self-control, helpfulness, justice, and responsibility, respectively. The students in the TCG and SEM groups showed more improvement in their helpfulness, friendship, and general value perception. Those in the TCG group improved more in responsibility and self-control than the CG and PAC groups. Physical education lesson attitudes of SEM, PAC, and TCG group students improved more than CG students. While there was a development in favor of males in self-control value, no significant difference was found in other values dimensions and course attitudes according to gender. A positive moderate relationship was found between students' value perceptions and course attitudes. In the focus group interview, the students in different groups interpreted the research findings in different ways. As a result of the research; TCG and SEM were at the forefront in the development of students' value perception, and PAC and TCG in the development of course attitudes. Based on these results, it is recommended that teachers teach lessons with different models, methods, and course materials.

Keywords: Attitude, Physical Activity Card, Physical Education and Sports, Secondary School Student, Sports Education Model, Traditional Children's Games, Value Perception

* This study is a part of Dr. Ahmet Temel's doctoral thesis under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Hüdaverdi Mamak.

1. Introduction

1.1 Value and attitude concept

Value is the special meanings we attach to something about its condition. It is the degree of materiality of a situation or object (Tepe, 2002: 346). Values, in essence, enable individuals to prioritize values in order to respond to social expectations. People's values and beliefs may differ. Value is also the belief that something is desirable or undesirable, and it guides attitudes (Güngör, 2018: 180). Individual's values; it fulfills the function of influencing, determining, regulating, directing, and managing attitudes and behaviors (Dilmaç, 2012: 2). The concepts of value and attitude are related to each other, and individuals develop attitudes toward situations through their value system. When the concept of attitude is examined; it is defined as the tendency of an individual to react cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally against a situation with the help of experience, motivation, and knowledge (İnceoğlu, 2011: 16). Individuals tend to behave depending on situational factors (Tavşancıl, 2018: 70). As can be understood from the definitions, individuals can gain values and attitudes through life, experience and learning (Kağıtçıbaşı & Cemalcılar, 2020: 143).

1.2 Value Education and Attitude

Schools conduct value education on a planned basis to create a common social value perception. Thus, while the students who receive values education in schools are adopting the basic values related to their character development, the value judgments of society are maintained by protecting them (Lovat, 2011). It is recommended that values education is built on the virtues of respect and responsibility (Lickona, 1992). In today's Turkey, values education has been added to the official curriculum with the title of "root values". Root values are classified as justice, honesty, friendship, patience, self-control, love, respect, responsibility, helpfulness, and patriotism (MNE, 2018). The role of physical education lessons is great in imparting these values to students and developing a positive attitude toward values (Kuter & Kuter, 2012). In physical education course, it is aimed that students develop a positive attitude by doing physical activities and become willing to participate in physical activity throughout their lives (Kangalgil et al., 2006). The teacher who conducts the physical education lesson can do the value education with different models, methods, styles, and course materials. Sports Education Models (SEM), Traditional Children's Games (TCG), Physical Activity Cards (PAC), and Traditional Methods can be used in value education (MNE, 2018).

SEM is a teaching model that supports students' more active and healthy life experiences and raises skilled, knowledgeable, and willing sports individuals. In this model, students learn team tactics and the behaviors of the second role they have acquired (coach, captain, outfitter, etc.) along with sport-specific skills (İnce et al., 2010: 47-48). Students develop responsibility, commitment, leadership, belonging, and learning skills by virtue of their roles (Anwar et al., 2019). Students develop skills, values, attitudes, and tactical strategies at the end of the SEM season.

The PAC, which is used to gain value for students in Turkey, was designed with reference to the "Top Play Sport (TOPs)" cards developed in England. TOPs have been produced in different contents according to the student's development levels. The "Top Play" yellow card group helps to gain basic motor skills in early childhood (5-9 years). The "Top Sport" sport card group was created to improve the physical fitness and movement skills of children in their second childhood (10-13 years) (Mirzeoğlu, 2017). Teachers can select and use cards related to the student's development level and course content. When teachers benefit from PAC in physical education classes, students enjoy the lessons, and their participation in classes increases (Esen & Mirzeoğlu, 2018). PAC has an important function in providing students with values such as tolerance, cooperation, and obeying the rules (Temel & Kangalgil, 2021).

Another way for societies to transfer their values to future generations is through games (Sümbüllü & Altınışık, 2016). The game; it takes the child away from egocentrism and makes him understand the feelings of others. Many moral concepts such as true-false, right-wrong, cooperation, communication, protecting rights and freedoms,

gaining national and moral values, and rules to be followed are learned during the game (Temel & Kangalgil, 2021). There are “Traditional Children's Games (TCG)” in which each society reflects its culture. TCG is fun and culturally valuable games that positively affect the development of children, improve their skills, and add universal value (Lestarininingrum, 2017). The child, playing the TCG, learns about being hopeful, obeying the rules, sharing, greeting, communication, self-control, determination, patience, honesty, and social roles (Fang et al., 2016; Lestari & Prima, 2017).

1.3 Introduce the Problem

Today's modern understanding of education has realized that raising students only cognitively by depriving them of values is a threat to society (Kenan, 2009). For this reason, education for cultural and universal values is carried out at all levels of formal education (Çimen et al., 2016). Especially in the years when students start school, they develop values and positive attitudes through identification with their teacher and friendships. When this critical period is passed, it is very difficult for students to change their emotions (Tavşancıl, 2018: 79-81). The attitudes of the students may vary according to the course content. For example, while boys like challenging movements, girls may like aesthetic movements (Liu et al., 2008). On the other hand, while students with good physical competency enjoyed competitive games, students with low skill levels did not like competitive games (Bernstein et al., 2011). Students who develop a positive attitude towards the physical education lesson reach their lesson goals more easily (Subramaniam & Silverman, 2007).

1.4 Explore Importance of the Problem

Considering the value studies in physical education lessons, it was found that there is generally a positive value perception at the secondary school level. Gender makes a difference as an important variable in the formation of value perception (Işıkgöz et al., 2018). In experimental studies, the intervention applied instead of gender was at the forefront (Burgueño & Medina-Casaubón, 2020). Value studies were generally carried out using the scanning model (Keleş & Yoncalık, 2019; Sağın & Karabulut, 2019). In the literature, it has been observed that students generally have a positive attitude toward secondary school physical education lessons (Kumar & Singh, 2011). Gender and grade level have been important predictors of course attitude (Kangalgil et al., 2006). Again, attitude studies were mostly carried out without using an intervention approach (Sivrikaya & Kılçık, 2018).

1.5 State Hypotheses and Their Correspondence to Research Design

It is known that young people who do sports for a long time through physical education classes develop self-control skills and display virtuous human behaviors away from aggression (Basiaga-Pasternak et al., 2020). With the acquisition of these values, the attitude of being willing to participate in physical activities is an important support for the success of the students. When students learn their attitudes, they will direct their careers in line with their interests (Çakmak Yıldızhan & Çağlayan, 2018). Proceeding from here, the research was conducted to examine the value perceptions and attitudes of secondary school 7th-grade students toward physical education and sports lessons. The study was carried out with 7th-grade students during a 10-week experiment, considering that the ability to understand, interpret and respond to measurement tools is better than the lower grade levels and that 8th-grade students are preparing for high school. It is thought that the results of the study will be important because of the use of different course contents in the experimental process and the examination of the value and attitude change together. In addition, quantitative and qualitative collection of study data will be beneficial in obtaining reliable results. After determining the effectiveness of the course content used, it is anticipated that the results of the study will contribute significantly to the literature.

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

This research is in a quasi-experimental model with the pretest-posttest control group. Since it is not possible to assign impartially while creating groups in educational institutions, an intervention approach is applied to ready groups. At the same time, the homogeneity of the pretest group scores is checked (Büyüköztürk et al., 2020: 203-205; Can, 2019: 14). In this direction, the content of the experimental studies were randomly assigned to the grade branches and the homogeneity assumption was fulfilled in the pre-test results. In the experimental groups, while the lessons were taught with the sports education model, physical activity card, and traditional children's games; in the control group, lessons were conducted with the traditional method. The intervention approaches applied to the groups and the situations affecting the physical education lesson value perception and attitude were examined.

2.2 Study Group

The study was carried out in Kayseri/Yeşilhisar in the 2nd semester of the 2020-2021 academic year. The study group consisted of 91 secondary school students attending the 7th grade in 2 different village schools. The students to be included in the study were selected according to the homogeneous sampling technique, one of the purposive sampling methods. Students studying in close villages and at the same grade level can be examined with this technique. Since at least 20 participants in the experimental groups gave reliable results (Büyüköztürk et al., 2020: 92-97), the study group was considered to be sufficient.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of students

Variable	Sub Categories	f	%	Total
Gender	Male	44	48.4	91
	Female	47	51.6	
Experimental groups	Sports Education Model (SEM)	23	25.3	
	Physical Activity Card (PAC)	22	24.2	
	Traditional Children's Games (TCG)	23	25.3	
	Conventional Method/Control Group (CG)	23	25.3	

2.3 Experimental Design

Students in the first village school formed SEM and CG; the second village school formed PAC and TCG. To obtain effective results in the application of SEM and other teaching methods, work should be carried out for more than 8 weeks (Hünük & Saraç Oğuzhan, 2017). Accordingly, it was assumed that the 10-week experimental period was sufficient.

Football season application was made in the SEM group. Since the class size is "23", 3 different teams consisting of "8-8-7" people were formed. The teams are named as "Ay Yıldız, Alfa, and Gönüllerin Birincisi". In line with their character and skills, the students in the team were given the duties of coach, assistant coach, conditioner, equipment man, statistician, paramedic, referee, and press. In the first 5 weeks, the coaches made their teams work on passing, dribbling, shooting, and position. During this time, students with other responsibilities supported their teams. In the second 5 weeks, league matches with points were held. At the festival held at the end of the season, the champion "Ay Yıldız" team was awarded certificates.

In the PAC group, "4 weeks football, 4 weeks volleyball and 2 weeks athletics" units were treated, and basic level Yellow PAC and branch-based Purple PAC were used. In the volleyball unit, the Yellow PAC "18- Getting used to the ball, 19- Throwing holding movements, 29- Target games, and 30- Throwing hitting" cards were used. Net and racket games from the Purple PAC group "1- Are you ready?, 2- Flying balls, 3- Receiving the bouncing ball, 4- Throw the serve, 5- Serve reception, 6- Far-close-sideways, 7- Two by two and 8- Earn points" cards were used. In the football unit, "19- Throwing-holding, 21- Kicking, 23- Stopping-control, 24- Dribbling, 27- Collecting the ball, and 28- Relay race" cards were used. From Purple PAC offensive games, "3- Pass, 4- Pass game, 5- Five pass, 7- Find space and 10- Wing game" cards; Purple PAC from hitting and catching games, "3- Hit the target, 6- Throw at the target, 7- Accurate shot and 9- Şırnak baseball" cards were used. In the athletics unit, "3- Running,

4- Jumping-bouncing, 5- Stepping and tabbing, 13- Jumping-touchdown, 15- Static balance, and 28- Relay race” cards from the Yellow PAC group were used.

The provincial directorate of national education organizes TCG festival and it includes castled dodgeball game, handkerchief snatch, and hopscotch games. These games were played by TCG students. Castled dodgeball game and handkerchief snatch game were applied for 4 weeks, and hopscotch games were applied for 2 weeks. Castled dodgeball game; It is a cooperative game that develops throwing-holding skills in a team of 8 people and includes attacking and defending. A team wins the game when it hits all the players in the opposing team or when the opponent makes a mistake. Handkerchief snatch game; It is a game that develops speed, attention, strategy, and cooperation skills in a team of 10 people. The opposing team must be completely eliminated to win the handkerchief snatch game. On the other hand, hopscotch is an 8-stage game that is played individually, and develops balance-attention skills. The student who is at the most advanced stage in 10 minutes compared to his opponent wins the game. During the experiment, these games were played by forming heterogeneous teams.

In the control group, the units (volleyball, football, athletics) used while teaching in the PAC group were applied with the traditional method under the supervision of the teacher.

2.4 Data Collection Tools

In the study, data were collected using an explanatory sequential design approach in the mixed method. In this method, the collection of data is quantitatively weighted. To allow for the explanation and elaboration of the quantitative data obtained, qualitative data on the subject are collected and the results are interpreted (Creswell, 2020: 707).

2.4.1 Physical Education and Sports Lesson Values Education Scale

28-item scale developed by Kangalgil et al., (2021) was used to learn students' perceptions of value. The 5-point Likert-type scale has a total of 5 dimensions: Responsibility, justice, helpfulness, self-control, and friendship. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of the scale is .93. While evaluating the scale; 1-1.79 points very negative, 1.80-2.59 points negative, 2.60-3.39 points medium, 3.40-4.19 points positive, and over 4.20 points very positive over the arithmetic mean interpreted as perception.

2.4.2 Physical Education and Sports Attitude Scale

A one-dimensional 24-item scale developed by Demirhan & Altay (2001) was used to learn students' attitudes toward physical education and sports lessons. The 5-point Likert-type scale has 12 positive and 12 negative items. Negative expressions are used with reverse coding. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of the scale is .93. While evaluating the scale; 1-1.79 points very negative, 1.80-2.59 points negative, 2.60-3.39 points average, 3.40-4.19 points positive, and above 4.20 points very negative over the arithmetic average interpreted as a positive attitude.

2.4.3 Collection of Qualitative Data

After the pre-test and post-test quantitative data collection, the students' most and least changing value perceptions and attitude expressions were determined. The determined statements were converted into questions and a focus group interview was conducted and recorded with a voice recorder. A total of 12 students, 3 from each group (SEM, PAC, TCG, and CG), participated in the interview. The sound recording was transferred to the word processing program exactly. In addition, the teacher's diary was used. A purposeful sample was chosen to ensure the external validity of the qualitative data. The students in the experimental groups were selected according to their skill level as good, medium, and bad. The credibility of the study was ensured by reading the interview forms to the students after the focus group interview. In the internal consistency reliability of the study, the data were re-examined and grouped at 4 weeks intervals. Thus, the details that the researcher might overlook over time were taken under control (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018: 273-282).

2.5 Ethical Aspect of Research

An ethical report was received from Niğde Ömer Halisdemir University Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee (dated 02/07/2020 and numbered 86837521-050.99-E-26846). To be able to implement the research after the ethical report, the study was carried out by obtaining research permission from the Kayseri Provincial Directorate of National Education (dated 27/07/2020 and numbered 94025929.02-E.9929856). With the help of data collection scales, pre-test measurements of the students were taken in February 2021. The researchers recorded their observations during the 10-week experiment by keeping a diary. Again, with the data collection scales, the post-test measurements of the students were taken in April 2021. A focus group meeting was held in May 2021 for the different results of the students between the posttest and pretest.

2.6. Evaluation of Data

In the analysis of quantitative data, arithmetic mean, frequency, standard deviation, and correlation analyzes were performed by using SPSS (Ver: 24.0) program. Since the data did not show normal distribution, Wilcoxon, Mann Whitney U, and Kruskal Wallis analysis from non-parametric tests were made in comparison, and a .05 significance level was taken into account. In experimental studies, the difference score should be calculated by using the pretest-posttest results to examine the effect of the applied intervention (Can, 2019: 258). Difference scores were obtained by subtracting the pre-test scores from the post-test scores of the students and the comparisons were made over the difference score.

The qualitative data of the research (diary and focus group interview) were analyzed by content analysis method. The purpose of content analysis is to explain the collected data (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018: 242). Close to each other data were brought together around certain concepts and were conveyed with direct quotations and the researcher's interpretation.

3. Results

3.1 Quantitative Results

Table 2: Pre-test-post-test, and difference scores of students' physical education lesson value perception and attitudes

Scale	Dimensions	Pre-test			Post-test		Difference
		N	$\bar{x}$	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD	
Value perception	Responsibility	91	4.22	.91	4.42	.74	.19
	Justice	91	4.10	.99	4.38	.75	.27
	Helpfulness	91	3.91	.82	4.29	.73	.37
	Self-control	91	3.96	.77	4.38	.75	.41
	Friendship	91	3.65	.90	4.11	.73	.46
	Whole scale	91	3.98	.74	4.30	.64	.31
Lesson attitude	Attitude scale	91	3.93	.61	4.33	.51	.40

While the students' responsibility value was found to be very positive in pre-experiment dimension; justice, helpfulness, self-control, friendship and positive value perceptions were found throughout the scale. After the experiment, there was a positive increase in the scores of the students. Thus, the perceptions of responsibility, justice, helpfulness, self-control, and value across the scale have reached a very positive level. Although there was a positive development in friendship value, students' perception of value could not reach a very positive level. According to the difference scores, the most development was in friendship value. Friendship was followed by the values of self-control, helpfulness, justice, and responsibility, respectively. Values that carry general judgments about family and country in the dimension of responsibility were the values that showed the least improvement.

While the pre-experiment physical education lesson attitudes of the students were positive, the post-experiment lesson attitudes reached a very positive level. When the difference scores of the students are looked at, the feelings of cooperation and the attitude of willingly participating in the lesson have developed the most. Believing that physical education lesson improves health was the attitude towards the lesson that showed the least improvement.

Table 3: Comparison of pretest-posttest scores of students' physical education lesson value perception and attitudes

Scale	Posttest-Pretest	Sequence	n	Rank average	Rank sum	z	p
Value perception	Responsibility	Negative	17	22.29	379.00	-	.000*
		Positive	42	33.12	1391.00		
		Equal	32				
	Justice	Negative	11	19.68	216.50	-	.000*
		Positive	37	25.93	959.50		
		Equal	43				
	Helpfulness	Negative	10	26.45	264.50	-	.000*
		Positive	61	37.57	2291.50		
		Equal	20				
	Self-control	Negative	13	29.88	388.50	-	.000*
		Positive	60	38.54	2312.50		
		Equal	18				
	Friendship	Negative	9	21.50	193.50	-	.000*
		Positive	59	36.48	2152.50		
		Equal	23				
Whole scale	Negative	9	17.83	160.50	-	.000*	
	Positive	73	44.42	3242.50			
	Equal	9					7.127
Lesson attitude	Attitude scale	Negative	11	32.82	361.00	-6.353	.000*
		Positive	73	43.96	3209.00		
		Equal	7				

*(p<.05)

In Table 3, the importance of the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the students regarding the physical education lesson value perceptions and attitudes was examined. It is understood from the number of students in the positive order that the students who participated in physical education activities generally changed their views positively. The positive change in student scores was found to be significant in favor of the posttest (p<.05).

Table 4: Comparison of physical education lesson value perception and attitude difference scores according to experimental groups

Scale	Dimensions	Group	n	Rank average	x ²	p	Difference
Responsibility		SEM	23	45.00	17.075	.001*	PAC, CG<TCG
		PAC	22	41.48			
		TCG	23	63.80			
		CG	23	33.52			
Justice		SEM	23	51.28	5.012	.171	
		PAC	22	40.41			
		TCG	23	52.26			
		CG	23	39.80			
Helpfulness		SEM	23	55.50	23.886	.000*	
		PAC	22	38.09			

Value perception	TCG	23	61.78	CG<SEM, TCG		
Self-control	CG	23	28.28	23.499	.000*	PAC, CG<TCG
	SEM	23	45.76			
	PAC	22	42.52			
	TCG	23	66.26			
Friendship	CG	23	29.30	14.075	.003*	CG<SEM, TCG
	SEM	23	49.37			
	PAC	22	48.39			
	TCG	23	57.00			
Whole scale	CG	23	29.35	37.390	.000*	PAC, CG<TCG
	SEM	23	52.41			
	PAC	22	38.25			
	TCG	23	69.22			
Lesson attitude	CG	23	23.78	10.891	.012*	CG<SEM, PAC, TCG
	SEM	23	49.20			
	PAC	22	53.41			
	TCG	23	51.22			
	CG	23	30.50			

*(p<.05) [SEM: Sports Education Model], [PAC: Physical Activity Card], [TCG: Traditional Children's Games], [CG: Control Group]

In Table 4, the difference scores between the pre-test and post-test scores were examined in terms of groups. Looking at the mean rank column, the highest value perception development was in the TCG group, and the least improvement was in CG. No significant difference was found in the development of the justice value in terms of groups ($p>.05$). Responsibility and self-control values of the TCG group were found to be significantly higher than those of PAC and CG students ($p<.05$). Helpfulness, friendship, and holistic values of SEM and TCG group students were found to be significantly higher than CG's ($p<.05$). At the same time, the TCG group achieved significantly higher scores than the PAC group on the whole scale ($p<.05$).

While the most improvement in the attitude scale was in the PAC group; the least improvement has been in CG. The course attitudes of the SEM, PAC, and TCG groups were found to be significantly more positive than CG ($p<.05$).

Table 5: Comparison of physical education lesson value perception and attitude difference scores by gender

Scale	Dimensions	Gender	n	Rank average	Rank sum	U	p
Value perception	Responsibility	Male	44	47.91	2108.00	950.000	.494
		Female	47	44.21	2078.00		
	Justice	Male	44	47.85	2105.50	952.500	.493
		Female	47	44.27	2080.50		
	Helpfulness	Male	44	49.72	2187.50	870.500	.191
		Female	47	42.52	1998.50		
	Self-control	Male	44	51.86	2282.00	776.000	.039*
		Female	47	40.51	1904.00		
	Friendship	Male	44	50.81	2235.50	822.500	.088
		Female	47	41.50	1950.50		
	Whole scale	Male	44	51.27	2256.00	802.000	.065
		Female	47	41.06	1930.00		
Lesson attitude	Attitude scale	Male	44	43.36	1908.00	918.000	.357
		Female	47	48.47	2278.00		

*(p<.05)

In Table 5, the comparison of the physical education lesson value perception and attitude difference scores according to the gender of the students was made. Considering the mean rank column, a significant improvement was achieved in favor of male students in the self-control dimension of the value perception scale ($p < .05$); no significant difference was found in other dimensions and overall scale ($p > .05$). In terms of the development of physical education lesson attitudes, there was no significant finding according to gender ($p > .05$).

Table 6: Value perception and attitude difference scores correlation analysis

		Value perception scale	Attitude scale
Value perception scale	r	1	.579**
	p		.000
Attitude scale	r	.579**	1
	p	.000	

*($p < .05$), **($p < .01$)

In Table 6, the relationship between students' value perceptions and attitude difference scores was examined. A positive ($r = .57$), significant relationship was found between the value perception scale and attitude scale scores ($p < .01$). When students acquire a positive perception of value in physical education lessons, they also develop a positive attitude toward the lesson.

3.2 Qualitative Results

In this section, the responses of the students to the focus group interview were examined. The answers were also supported by the teacher's diary. Students were given appropriate coding and their opinions were directly conveyed. While coding; the gender (M, F) of the experimental group (SEM, PAC, TCG, CG) in which the student was present was given at the beginning and the sequence number (1, 2) at the end. The encodings are finally listed as M-SEM-1, F-PAC-1, M-TCG-1, and F-CG-1.

At the end of the experiment process, the friendship and helpfulness values of the students developed the most. M-SEM-1 on the value of not exaggerating joy and being humble when the game is won: *"We should not humiliate the other side. I am a person who pays a lot of attention to respect. Respect was also at the forefront during the football season, which we practiced in our lesson"* he replied, referring to his character and the characteristics of SEM. M-CG-1 said, *"We can be defeated in the game. If our opponent shows excessive joy, I get sad. That's why I try not to exaggerate my joy when we win"* and emphasized the importance of playing with empathy. M-PAC-2, on the other hand, said, *"If exaggerated joy is made against me, I do not welcome it. If we rejoice excessively, our friends' hearts may break, they may be sad"* he said about the negativities that exaggerated joy will cause. F-TCG-1: *"There is winning and losing in the game. Enjoying the game is more important than joy"* she argued that the game should focus on enjoying it more than winning. M-CG-3: *"I take care of this when I play with my friends from my own school. But when I play with other schools, it may not be so"* he argued that the joy may change according to the characteristics of the opponent. The students who took part in all groups experienced joy during the activities in order to live their joy in moderation and not to offend their friends (Researcher's diary).

Although students experience winning and losing situations in physical education lessons, M-SEM-3 partially agreed with this opinion. M-SEM-3: *"We had sharing, but we were divided into teams, our exchanges were only with our team. We have not entered into cooperation with other teams"* and drew attention to the fact that sharing is limited to team members. F-TCG-1: *"We can't win a game by ourselves. For example, we pass to each other in the game and shoot players. Let's throw the ball as well as we want. If our friend in front of us doesn't keep the ball well, we can't win the game. Winning is a team job"* she argued that it would not be possible to win games without help. F-PAC-3, who approaches the concept of helping more emotionally, said, *"In general, this sharing happens between girls and girls, boys and boys. If we do not share during the lessons, our friends will not play with us. Doing sports alone is not a good thing at all. If I stay alone, I won't do sports"* she said, referring to the fact that there is cooperation between the same gender in order not to be alone.

After the practice, the students valued the act of “being able to show tolerance when teammates make mistakes during the game”. F-TCG-1 “*There will be those who make mistakes in games so that they will be winners. How will we determine the winner if people don't make mistakes? That's why it's normal to make mistakes*” and mentioned that it is normal to make mistakes like winning. F-SEM-2: “*I look at the person who made the mistake. If he is someone who is far from sports, there is no point in being too hard on him*” she stressed that imposing responsibility on someone whose skill level is insufficient will not bring benefits. M-PAC-2: “*I can accept it if there are few mistakes made in the game, but I will not accept it if the same mistake is constantly repeated*” he pointed out that the reaction to the amount of mistakes changes. M-CG-2: “*Normally, I cannot tolerate a person who makes mistakes, but the same is not true for my friends.*” It has been observed that the student has no tolerance for mistakes, but is tolerant toward his friends with whom he has emotional intimacy. The same student was exposed to the reaction of his teammates when he constantly made mistakes during the game. Students with leadership roles reduced the pressure on their friends by directing the in-game positions to different positions. All players made mistakes in the game and understood that it is normal to make mistakes. It was found that those in the SEM group were focused on success; those in the TCG and PAC groups had fun; and in the CG, playing with close friends was more valuable (Researcher's diary).

At the end of the experiment process, little improvement was seen in the students' responsibility values related to family, environment, and country. F-SEM-2: “*We took in-game tasks in our lesson. These missions were not family related*” and argued that SEM missions were limited to in-game. M-PAC-2 contributed to this view with the statement “*There were no situations involving family roles in the games we played*”. M-PAC-3: “*Environmental responsibilities should be explained in every lesson. Then we will understand these issues better*” he argued that environmental responsibilities cannot be acquired with a single course alone. The students did not avoid taking responsibility for their course practices and duly fulfilled every responsibility given. As a result of the interviews with the students, it was determined that they did not know enough about their responsibilities about their family, environment and country (Researcher's diary).

It has been determined that students show little improvement in forming equal and fair teams with equal powers. M-CG-2: “*Winning is important to us. Our success is praised by our environment*” and mentioned that playing on the same team with talented students is important for winning. M-SEM-1: He believes that there should be equal forces in the game for the sustainability of the struggle, with the statement “*If all the strong people gather in the same place, the matches end immediately without rivalry*”. F-TCG-1 said, “*Instead of winning and losing, I prefer to play with my friends who respect me. Therefore, instead of equality, we should be a team of good friends*” she is in favor of making a value-oriented choice, not a winning one. Students in the SEM group found the choices fair as they were formed in a heterogeneous way. CG, which made the competitions with same genders, wanted to get the strong player. While the teams were being formed, the equality was preserved as the players were chosen in turn. The desire to play with close friends was observed in the PAC and TCG groups (Researcher's diary).

After the experiment process, the students' cooperative working attitude improved very well. M-SEM-3: “*We have prepared a board with our team. We have done the research. Someone wrote, someone made a design. We fulfilled our roles to win*” he said, referring to the characteristics of SEM. F-TCG-1: “*When playing castled dodgeball game, if the shooter and the catcher do not play in harmony, they cannot be successful. Sometimes we are confused about which opponent to throw the ball to in the game. What we cannot see, our teammates can see more easily. That's why cooperation is essential to win*” she said, referring to the harmonious action of attack and defense. M-PAC-2: “*Those who can do the challenging activities in our lessons help those who can't. We didn't make fun of our failed friends. Thus, everyone participated in the lesson with pleasure*”, referring to peer cooperation, and a positive attitude towards the lesson developed with the disappearance of pressure. F-CG-1: “*It was very nice to play team games, to do something together*” she explained the positive feature of working together. In SEM and TCG, feelings of belonging to a group and achievement were more pronounced (Researcher's diary).

The students' "believing that physical education activities contribute to the healthy development of people" showed limited improvement. M-SEM-3: “*Sometimes I have pain in the lesson. My knee bleeds when I fall. When I am very tired, I find it difficult to wake up in the morning*”, drawing attention to fatigue and disability. F-PAC-3: “*It improves our health at events. Once we used to get out of breath at the beginning of the lesson, now we don't get*

tired even at the end of the second lesson” she said, referring to the fact that physical education activities improve the respiratory system. M-CG-2: *“Most of our friends can't do push-ups. We have had so many physical education lessons, they still fail. A healthy person should do push-ups”* and drew attention to the existence of students who had difficulties in physical education class. Parallel to the change in physical parameters, students showed improvement in in-class activities. Some of them started to breathe more easily, some of them were able to do more push-ups. Of course, there were students who could not improve in this process (Researcher's diary).

The attitude of the students to do sports in their leisure time has shown little improvement due to environmental factors. M-PAC-2: He mentioned the lack of playgrounds with the statement *“I want to do sports, but there is no suitable sports area in our village”*. M-CG-3, on the other hand, emphasized the lack of necessary sports materials by saying *“We cannot find the materials for the sports we want to do”*. M-SEM-3: *“We were not allowed to go out due to the Covid virus. We also played phone games at home”*, it is seen that students do not have the opportunity to exercise in their free time. The Covid-19 Pandemic has caused students not to develop their leisure exercise attitudes at the desired level (Researcher's diary).

4. Discussion

4.1 Value Perception

It is known that students acquire the root values in the physical education curriculum and develop behaviors in this direction (Aydın et al., 2022; Koh et al., 2017). Students internalized the values of obeying the rules, respect, responsibility, cooperation, awareness, and willingness to participate in the national feast (Yıldız & Kangalgil, 2021). Keleş & Yoncalık (2019) determined that secondary school students acquired the values of courage-leadership, responsibility, respect, friendship, justice, self-confidence, helpfulness, Atatürkism, patriotism, hard work, and empathy at a very good level in physical education and sports lessons. Similarly, Muñoz-Llerena et al., (2022) concluded that the students who follow the physical education lesson are capable of respecting individual differences, standing up against obstacles, and enabling their learning. Related studies support the findings of the study. The students experienced the joy of participating in the games in moderation, and they formed in-game friendships by sharing their feelings of winning and losing with their friends. Students do not tend to exhibit the desired behaviors in all situations. In an extremely competitive physical education lesson environment, students may disregard moral values (Albouza et al., 2022). When we look at the findings of the study, the students were similarly able to react sharply to the amount of error and the person who made the mistake. As the passion for winning increases in the game, students may exhibit undesirable behaviors.

4.1.1 The Role of Experimental Groups in the Formation of Value Perception

Responsibility, justice, benevolence, self-control, and friendship value perceptions of the students who study physical education and sports lessons with the help of the “Sports Education Model (SEM)” have improved. The development of SEM students was better than the control group. The research of Bessa et al., (2021) showed that the SEM group students had higher self-confidence compared to the students who taught with the traditional method. Reinforcement and rewarding approaches are frequently used to increase the incidence of desired behaviors in students. Ediş & Gündüz (2019) also gave the “Blue Card” award for the correct behavior of the group that he taught with SEM. In addition to the model-based course, positive developments were observed in the values of respect, tolerance, and cooperation, with the students receiving awards. SEM helps students adapt to social rules and conventions. Burgueño & Medina-Casabón (2020) found that SEM contributes to the values of respect for social contracts, respect for rules, respect for referees and respect for the opponent. For SEM to be effective in adding value to students, students must believe and approve of ethical contracts (Harvey et al., 2011). In this direction, students participating in the study were asked to act ethically by signing ethical contract forms. In this regard, all students acted in accordance with the value of justice. Again, the students said that they wanted to “winning by deserving” as a reward for their efforts.

A development was observed in the value perceptions of the students who taught the physical education and sports lesson with the “Physical Activity Card (PAC)” course material. The development of the PAC group in self-control

and overall value perception was more limited than in the TCG group. In addition to the teacher-centered course execution, the use of PAC course material was effective in developing students' positive value perception. In the research of Temel & Kangalil (2021), primary school teachers who conducted their lessons with PAC made significant development. As a result of the study, students gained the values of obeying the rules, responsibility, respect, cooperation, awareness, and willingness to participate in the national feast. Physical activity games are very effective in the character development of students. In this direction, as a result of the students doing the activities in the course material, they experienced a significant change in the values of honesty, helpfulness, responsibility, and citizenship (Yalız Solmaz & Bayrak, 2016). Based on the findings of the study, it was understood that the use of PAC in the teaching of the lessons could be an alternative to the traditional method.

The development of the "Traditional Children's Games (TCG)" group in other value dimensions was better than the control group, except for the justice value. Traditional games are frequently used in transferring the values of a culture to future generations (Gelislı & Yazıcı, 2015; Hidayati, 2020). When the TCG group played traditional games, they liked the lesson activities because they could communicate effectively with their environment. The students told their parents about the games they played in the physical education class and had a pleasant conversation with their parents about the game. This case will contribute to the formation of cultural unity between the parent and the child. Damayani et al., (2019) concluded that students playing traditional games in Indonesia gain values such as honesty, leadership, cooperation, and awareness. Healthy character development is provided for students who gain basic moral values through traditional games (Dewi et al., 2020; Lestari & Prima, 2017). Different traditional games develop different value judgments of students. Bozkurt & Sözer (2017) found that Turkish children effectively acquire values such as responsibility, cooperation, self-confidence, and respect by playing games such as handkerchief snatch, castled dodgeball game, seven tiles, and gold bracelets. TCG students avoided negative behaviors by acquiring basic values. Especially the students, who put winning in the background, attributed meaning to the values rather than playing in the strong team in the matchups.

4.1.2 Perception of Value and Gender

Male and female students developed similar value perceptions in the dimensions of responsibility, justice, helpfulness, and friendship. Carlson & Hastie (1997) also found similarities in leadership, cooperation, and sportsmanship values of male and female students after physical education lessons with SEM. In the experimental studies applied in the literature, it was concluded that male and female students developed similar value perceptions (Büyükköse et al., 2016; Engin & Uygun, 2014). This shows that intervention approaches are fit for purpose. However, the value perceptions of male and female students may differ. It was concluded that in physical education lessons, female students were better in respect, national culture and togetherness, awareness, and healthy life values (Işıkgöz et al., 2018). Again, female students' perceptions of responsibility (Zekioğlu et al., 2020) and justice (Kapan & Gökçe, 2016) are quite high. The PAC group participating in the study also stated that they cooperate with same gender friends in the game. The female students attempted to help each other according to the characteristics of the game. This situation was also reflected outside the game, and an increase was observed in the cooperation behaviors of the students. Another result of the study is that male students showed better improvement in self-control value than female. Yıldız & Özgül (2017) found that male students are more inclined to sports than female students. The self-control values of male students have improved better with their tendency to sports (Aydoğan et al., 2016). The male students who participated in the research argued that the game of football is specific to male. The students were close to the idea that girls cannot play football like a boy no matter how hard they try. In this respect, it was determined that the students could not reach the desired level in terms of education.

4.2 Physical Education Lesson Attitude

The attitudes of secondary school students toward physical education lessons are significantly higher than other formal education steps (Sertkahya & Üren, 2021; Taşdemir et al., 2021). The results obtained in the literature are similar to the results of the study. In the study of Özsarı & Öztürk Çelik (2021), the attitudes towards the physical education lesson of the students whose social relations got weak were found to be in medium level. This result showed that social relations are an important variable that predicts physical education course attitudes. Based on

the importance of social relations, the students who participated in the study stated that they won the games by helping each other and that they enjoyed playing with their close friends. In addition to social relations, it is known that students with good academic achievement have positive physical education course attitudes (Subramaniam & Silverman, 2007). The students, who stated that they did not have low grades in the physical education lesson, stated that they participated in the lesson with pleasure. Students with good body image (Kamtsios & Digelidis, 2008) and skill level (Bernstein et al., 2011) enjoy competitive physical education lessons. In line with the literature, the student group, who participated in the competitive games, adopted winning by struggling. To win by working hard was found valuable.

4.2.1 The Role of Experimental Groups in the Formation of Physical Education Lesson Attitude

In the study, the attitudes of the students who participated in the physical education lesson with the “Sports Education Model (SEM)” are higher than the students who teach with the traditional method. When the lesson is taught with differentiated lesson contents, students develop positive attitudes toward physical education lesson (Özbal et al., 2019). Thus, SEM emerges as an important supporter in physical education lessons (Doydu et al., 2013). Wallhead et al. (2013) followed the progress of the students who participated in the physical education lesson through SEM for 4 seasons. Students received training in ground hockey, basketball, volleyball and handball during the seasons. At the end of the study, the students who participated in SEM for a long time enjoyed their sports experiences by improving their social bonds with their peers. Luna et al., (2019) found that at the end of the SEM season, students' subjective well-being levels were high and they were able to control their emotions. Students who were able to regulate their emotions enjoyed the course content. Similarly, in the findings of the study, there was an increase in the course attitudes of the members of the SEM group, as they experienced the feeling of being a part of a group and achieving. A positive attitude toward the course enables students to gain school belonging (Filiz, 2018). Students who started face-to-face education after the Covid-19 Pandemic and participated in physical education lesson activities stated that they enjoyed school and physical education lessons.

With the help of the “Physical Activity Card (PAC)”, the attitude of the group participating in the physical education lesson towards the lesson was measured at a very good level. The PAC group was the group that enjoyed the physical education lesson the most. Atlı et al., (2018) examined the results of conducting the physical education lesson with PAC in addition to the peer teaching model. At the end of the process, the course attitudes of secondary school students increased. At the same time, students found the lesson fun, understandable and increasing participation. The use of PAC as an alternative to the traditional method allows students to develop positive feelings and academic motivation towards the lesson (Ağırtaş, 2017; Öztürk, 2019). So much so that the PAC group in the study stated that they wanted to learn new information and receive feedback from their teacher. Students, whose needs were met, had the opportunity to play games with their close friends and developed a positive attitude toward the lesson.

The physical education lesson attitude of the group that played “Traditional Children's Games (TCG)” developed like the other experimental groups. Istarahayu (2020) found that the national Lompat Tali game gave students a cooperative working attitude. In their research, Syihabbudin & Umami (2021) concluded that the traditional game called Gobak Sodor gave students an attitude of tolerance. Romanvican et al., (2020) also found that the traditional game called Engklek gives an attitude of tolerance. Traditional games are frequently used to develop students' moral values and attitudes. TCG members showed interest in traditional games played by their parents. TCG group enjoyed chatting about traditional games with their parents and friends.

4.2.2 Physical Education Lesson Attitude and Gender

There was no significant gender difference in the development of the course attitudes of the students who are subject to physical education and sports courses with different course contents. The results of the research conducted with secondary school students in the literature also confirm the findings of the study (Gürbüz & Özkan, 2012; Keskin et al., 2016; Kılıç & Çimen, 2018). When the lesson activities are designed with different contents, male and female students enjoy the physical education lesson. It is also a known fact that male students' participation in physical education classes is high (Yıldız & Özgül, 2017). Male students with high participation

in lesson activities had more positive lesson attitudes compared to female students (Cengiz et al., 2018; Kumar & Singh, 2011). Today, female students' participation in sports has increased significantly. With the intense participation in the lesson, female students showed more positive attitudes toward the physical education lesson (Taşdemir et al., 2021). Positive results are obtained when the lesson is conducted with different contents for male and female students.

4.3 Value and Attitude Relationship

It was observed that when students' beliefs about root values increased, their attitudes toward physical education and sports lessons increased. Looking at the literature, it was seen that there were positive and significant relationships between students' social life skills, competence, and course attitude (Balyan et al., 2012; Keskin et al., 2016). Physical education lesson is an important argument for strengthening friendship bonds and developing positive attitudes based on cooperation between students (Gülây et al., 2010; Özbal et al., 2019). As the human values of the students develop, they develop a positive attitude and environmental sensitivity towards their environment (Eser, 2012). When students' values and attitudes toward a subject are significantly high, it emerges as behavior (Yılmaz & Aytekin, 2020). People's values predict their attitudes and behaviors. The high values and attitudes developed in the physical education lesson are promising.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

As a result of the research, the value perceptions and attitudes of the students participating in the physical education lesson have developed. During the experiment, the highest development was seen in the value of friendship, while the highest score was obtained in the value of responsibility. TCG and SEM were at the forefront in the development of value perception, and PAC and TCG groups in the development of attitude. Females and males showed similar development. When the qualitative findings are examined; Students who behaved respectfully towards their friends during the game did not experience excessive joy. Emotions such as winning and losing the in the SEM group are experienced within the same team; The PAC group, on the other hand, stated that these feelings were experienced among the same gender friends. Errors in the game are considered normal according to the amount of mistakes made. In physical education lessons, students think that family, environment, and country values are not directly emphasized. The students did not make good progress in behaving equally while forming teams. The fact that their sense of winning was at the forefront and that they wanted to play in the same team with their close friends. The groups explained the good level of cooperation attitudes differently. SEM group students associated their high cooperation attitudes with the division of labor in their SEM group roles; TCG group students with fulfilling their in-game roles in winning the game; PAC students with helping their friends who have difficulties in doing PAC group activities; CG explained that team games allow sharing. Due to the fatigue, disability or weakness experienced in the lessons, the students did not agree that the physical education lesson improves health.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, it is recommended that teachers who conduct physical education classes benefit from SEM, TCG, and PAC in their lessons. In addition to the contents of this course, the effects of individual and social responsibility model and tactical game model approaches can be examined. It is recommended that similar studies be conducted on different sample groups.

References

Ağırtaş, R. (2017). *Ortaokullarda beden eğitimi ve spor dersinde akran eğitiminin etkililiği fiziksel etkinlik kartlarının kullanımı (Elazığ il örneği)* [The effectiveness of peer education in physical education and sports

- lessons in secondary schools: Use of physical activity cards (Elazığ province example)]. Unpublished Master Thesis. Firat University Institute of Health Sciences, Elazığ.
- Albouza, Y., Chazaud, P., & Wach, M. (2022). Athletic identity, values and self-regulatory efficacy governing hypercompetitive attitudes. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 58, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2021.102079>
- Anwar, A. S., Hendrayana, Y., & Ma'mun, A. (2019). *The development of responsibility and leadership through esport education model*. 4th International Conference on Sport Science, Health, and Physical Education (ICSSPE) Atlantis Press.
- Atlı, K., Mirzeoğlu, A. D., & Erkut, O. (2018). Akran öğretim modeli ve fiziksel etkinlik kartları uygulamalarına ilişkin öğrenci görüşleri [The student views about applications of the peer teaching model and physical activity cards in secondary school]. *Türkiye Klinikleri Spor Bilimleri*, 10(3), 97-115. <https://doi.org/10.5336/sportsci.2018-60112>
- Aydın, E., Temel, A., & Kangalgil, M. (2022). Geçmişten günümüze ortaöğretim beden eğitimi ve spor dersi öğretim programlarının incelenmesi [Investigation of the secondary physical education and sports lesson curriculum from past to present]. *Journal of Global Sport and Education Research*, 5(1), 99-117. <https://doi.org/10.55142/jogser.1113312>
- Aydoğan, H., Bardakçı, S., Arslan, E., Civelek, H., & İşyar, Z. (2016). İlkokul 4. sınıf ve ortaokul 5. sınıf öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi dersine yönelik tutum ve öz-yeterliklerinin incelenmesi [Examining of self-efficacies and attitudes of 4th grades primary school and 5th grades middle school students towards physical education course]. *CBÜ Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 11(2), 100-119. <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/cbubesbd/issue/32244/357859>
- Balyan, M., Balyan, K. Y., & Kiremitçi, O. (2012). Farklı sportif etkinliklerin ilköğretim 2. kademe öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi dersine yönelik tutum, sosyal beceri ve öz yeterlik düzeylerine etkisi [Effects of different sporting events on 2nd level elementary school students' attitude towards physical education and sport lessons, social skills and self efficacy]. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 14(2), 196-201. <https://search.trdizin.gov.tr/yayin/detay/148944/>
- Basiaga-Pasternak, J., Szafraniec, Ł., Jaworski, J., & Ambroży, T. (2020). Aggression in competitive and non-competitive combat sports athletes. *Ido Movement for Culture. Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology*, 20(2), 17-23. <https://doi.org/10.14589/ido.20.2.3>
- Bernstein, E., Phillips, S. R., & Silverman, S. (2011). Attitudes and perceptions of middle school students toward competitive activities in physical education. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 30(1), 69-83. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.30.1.69>
- Bessa, C., Hastie, P., Rosado, A., & Mesquita, I. (2021). Sport education and traditional teaching: influence on students' empowerment and self-confidence in high school physical education classes. *Sustainability*, 13(2), 578. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020578>
- Bozkurt, E., & Sözer, M. A. (2017). Çocuk oyunları ile değerler eğitimi [Values education with children's games]. *The Journal of Academic Social Sciences*, 55, 295-323. <http://dx.doi.org/10.16992/ASOS.12844>
- Burgueño, R., & Medina-Casabón, J. (2020). Sport education and sportsmanship orientations: An intervention in high school students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 17(3), 837. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17030837>
- Büyükköse, A., Yıldırım Orhan, Ş., & Şeren, M. (2016). Amatör müzik eğitiminin, ortaokul öğrencilerinin problem çözme becerilerine etkisi (Kırıkkale ili örneği) [Impacts of amateur music education on the problem solving skills of secondary school students (sample of kırıkale)]. *Turkish Studies*, 11(21), 565-582. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7827/TurkishStudies.9914>
- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Çakmak, E. K., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2020). *Eğitimde bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri [Scientific research methods in education]*. 28. Edition. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Can, A. (2019). *Spss ile bilimsel araştırma sürecinde nicel veri analizi [Quantitative data analysis in the scientific research process with SPSS]*. 8. Edition. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Carlson, T. B., & Hastie, P. A. (1997). The student social system within sport education. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 16(2), 176-195. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1997-07720-002>
- Cengiz, Ö., Kılıç, M. A., & Soylu, Y. (2018). Ortaokul öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi dersine yönelik tutumlarının incelenmesi [Investigation of the attitudes of secondary school students on physical education]. *Sosyal Bilimler Akademi Dergisi*, 1(2), 141-149. <https://doi.org/10.38004/sobad.480851>
- Creswell, J. W. (2020). *Eğitim araştırmaları nicel ve nitel araştırmanın planlanması, yürütülmesi ve değerlendirilmesi [Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research]*. 3rd Edition. Ankara: Edam. (Translation Editor: Ekşi, H.).
- Çakmak Yıldızhan, Y., & Çağlayan, G. (2019). Öğrencilerin beden eğitimi dersine yönelik tutumları ile sosyal zekâ düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi [Investigating the relationship between attitudes of students towards physical education lesson and their social intelligence levels]. *Gazi Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 24(4), 227-240. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/gbesbd/issue/49196/568424>

- Çimen, S., Öztürk, F., Özcan, A. F., Özkan, A., & Balkaş, S. R. (2016). Değerler eğitime yönelik kültürler arası karşılaştırmalı bir araştırma: Almanya, İsveç, güney kore ve malezya örneği [An inter cultural contrastive study on the education of values: Samples from germany, sweden, south korea and malaysia]. *Akademik Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 4(30), 629-649. <https://doi.org/10.16992/ASOS.1266>
- Damayani, N. A., Saepudin, E., Budiono, A., & Rachmawati, T. S. (2019). Preservation of traditional game values as educational tourism assets in sindangkereta district, indonesia. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 4(36), 735-745. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v10.4\(36\).04](https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v10.4(36).04)
- Demirhan, G., & Altay, F. (2001). Lise birinci sınıf öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi ve spora ilişkin tutum ölçeği II [Attitude scale of high school first graders towards physical education and sport II]. *Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 12(2), 9-20. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/sbd/issue/16421/171534>
- Dewi, N. R., Saputri, E., Nurkhalisa, S., & Akhlis, I. (2020). The effectiveness of multicultural education through traditional games-based inquiry toward improving student scientific attitude. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 1567 042051. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1567/4/042051>
- Dilmaç, B. (2002). *İnsanca değerler eğitimi [Humane values education]*. 1st Edition. Ankara: Nobel Publication Distribution.
- Doydu, İ., Çelen, A., & Çoknaz, H. (2013). Spor eğitimi modeli'nin öğrencilerin beden eğitimi ve spora karşı tutumuna etkisi [The effect of the sports education model on the attitudes of students towards physical education and sports]. *e-Uluslararası Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 4(2), 99-110. <http://www.e-ijer.com/tr/pub/issue/8022/105386>
- Ediş, M., & Gündüz, N. (2019). Spor eğitim modeliyle işlenen futbol etkinliğinde mavi kart uygulaması öğretmen ve öğrenci görüşleri [Blue card application in soccer event with sport training model: teacher and student opinions]. *SPORMETRE Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 17(4), 158-171. <https://doi.org/10.33689/spormetre.576747>
- Engin, G., & Uygun, S. (2014). The effectiveness of language arts and physical education curriculum integrated with values education program/Türkçe ve beden eğitimi öğretim programları ile bütünleştirilmiş değerler eğitimi programının etkililiği. *Eğitimde Kuram ve Uygulama*, 10(4), 942-969. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/eku/issue/5462/74132>
- Esen, E., & Mirzeoğlu, A. D. (2018). Beden eğitimi ve spor derslerinde kullanılan fiziksel etkinlik kartlarının akademik öğrenme zamanına etkisi [The effects of physical activity cards used in physical education courses on academic learning time]. *Kastamonu Eğitim Dergisi*, 26(4), 1091-1100. <https://doi.org/10.24106/kefdergi.433411>
- Eser, A. (2012). *İlköğretim ikinci kademe öğrencilerinin insani değerler düzeyleri ile çevresel tutumları arasındaki ilişki [The relationship between the levels of human values and environmental attitudes of secondary school students]*. Unpublished Master Thesis. Yeditepe University Institute of Social Sciences, İstanbul.
- Fang, Y., Chen, K., & Huang, Y. (2016). Emotional reactions of different interface formats: comparing digital and traditional board games. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, 8(3), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1687814016641902>
- Filiz, M. A. (2018). *Ortaokul çağındaki çocukların beden eğitimi ve spor dersine yönelik tutumları ile okula bağlanma düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi [Examining the relationship between secondary school children's attitudes towards physical education and sports lessons and their level of attachment to school]*. Unpublished Master Thesis. Marmara University Institute of Education Sciences, İstanbul.
- Gelisli, Y., & Yazici, E. (2015). A study into traditional child games played in konya region in terms of development fields of children. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 197, 1859-1865. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.07.247>
- Gülay, O., Mirzeoğlu, D., & Çelebi, M. (2010). Effects of cooperative games on social skill levels and attitudes toward physical education. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research (EJER)*, 10(40), 77-92. https://ejer.com.tr/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/ejer_2010_issue_40.pdf
- Güngör, E. (2018). *Doktora, doçentlik, profesörlük tezleri [PhD, associate professorship, professorship theses]*. 1st Edition. İstanbul: Yer-Su Publishing.
- Gürbüz, A., & Özkan, H. (2012). Determining the attitude of secondary school students towards physical education and sport lesson (Muğla sample). *Pamukkale Journal of Sport Sciences*, 3(2), 78-89. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/psbd/issue/20577/219231>
- Harvey, S., Kirk, D., & O'Donovan, T. M. (2011). Sport education as a pedagogical application for ethical development in physical education and youth sport. *Sport, Education and Society*, 19(1), 41-62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2011.624594>
- Hidayati, N. N. (2020). Indonesian traditional games: A way to implant character education in children and preserve indonesian local wisdom. *Istawa: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 5(1), 81-101. <https://doi.org/10.24269/ijpi.v5i1.2475>
- Hünük, D., & Saraç Oğuzhan, N. (2017). *Spor eğitim modeli (sem), model temelli beden eğitimi öğretimi [Sports education model (sem), model-based physical education teaching]*. 1st Edition. (Editor: Mirzeoğlu, A. D.) Ankara: Spor Publishing House and Bookstore.

- Istirahayu, L. (2020). Enhancement of students cooperation attitude through traditional game of lompat tali. *Journal of Education, Teaching and Learning*, 5(2), 249-252. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/218678/>
- Işıkgöz, M. E., Esentaş, M., & Işıkgöz, M. (2018). Ortaokul öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi ve spor dersine yönelik değer düzeylerinin çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi: Batman il örneği [Examination of value levels of secondary school students towards physical education and sports lesson in terms of various variables: Batman province example]. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 4(4), 661-676. <https://doi.org/10.24289/ijsser.464221>
- İnce, M. L., Cengiz, C., Ebem, Z., Hünük, D., Kangalgil, M., Saçlı, F., Saraç, L., & Yapar, A. (2010). *Spor eğitimi modeli. Öğretim modelleri ve güncel araştırmalar [Sports training model. Teaching models and current research]*. Ankara: Spor Publishing House and Bookstore.
- İnceoğlu, M. (2011). *Tutum algı iletişim [Attitude perception communication]*. 6th Edition. Ankara: Siyasal Bookstore.
- Kağıtçıbaşı, Ç., & Cemalcılar, Z. (2020). *Dünden bugüne insan ve insanlar sosyal psikolojiye giriş [Human and people from past to present introduction to social psychology]*. 23. Edition. İstanbul: Evrim Publishing House.
- Kamtsios, S., & Digelidis, N. (2008). Physical activity levels, exercise attitudes, self-perceptions and bmi type of 11 to 12-year-old children. *Journal of Child Health Care*, 12(3), 232-240. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1367493508092510>
- Kangalgil, M., Hünük, D., & Demirhan, G. (2006). İlköğretim, lise ve üniversite öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi ve spora ilişkin tutumlarının karşılaştırılması [Comparison of elementary school, high school and university students' attitudes toward physical education and sport]. *Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 17(2), 48-57. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/sbd/issue/16401/171457>
- Kangalgil, M., Özgül, F., Temel, A., Kural, T., & Karagöz, Y. (2021). Beden eğitimi ve spor dersi değerler eğitimi ölçeği (bededöe) geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması [Validity and reliability study of physical education and sports lesson values education scale (peslves)]. *Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 15(1), 70-80. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/bsd/issue/60685/855962>
- Kapan, E., & Gökçe, N. (2016). 7. sınıf öğrencilerinin sosyal bilgiler dersindeki değerleri kazanma durumlarının incelenmesi [The study of 7th grade students' gain values situations in social studies course]. *Kesit Akademi Dergisi*, (6), 84-105. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/kesitakademi/issue/59840/864752>
- Keleş, M., & Yoncalık, O. (2019). Beden eğitimi ve spor dersi ve ilköğretim sekizinci sınıf öğrencilerinde değerler eğitimi [Physical education and sport lesson and values education in the 8th grade secondary school students]. *Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 13(3), 230-237. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/bsd/issue/50922/664493>
- Kenan, S. (2009). Modern eğitimde kaybolan nokta: Değerler eğitimi [The missing dimension of modern education: Values education]. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri*, 9(1), 259-295. <https://search.trdizin.gov.tr/yayin/detay/90078/>
- Keskin, N., Öncü, E., & Küçük, K. S. (2016). Ortaokul öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi dersine yönelik tutum ve öz-yeterlikleri [Attitudes and self-efficacy of middle school students toward physical education classes]. *SPORMETRE Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 14(1), 93-107. https://doi.org/10.1501/Sporm_0000000287
- Kılıç, T., & Çimen, P. N. (2018). Ortaokul ve lise öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi ve spor dersine karşı tutumlarının incelenmesi [Examining the attitudes of the secondary school and high school students towards physical education and sports lesson]. *Akdeniz Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1(1), 1-13. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/asbid/issue/40817/442686>
- Koh, K. T., Camiré, M., Lim Regina, S. H., & Soon, W. S. (2017). Implementation of a values training program in physical education and sport: A follow-up study. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 22(2), 197-211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2016.1165194>
- Kumar, A., & Singh, S. (2011). Attitudes toward physical education and sports of secondary school students of Delhi. *GYANODAYA-The Journal of Progressive Education*, 4(1), 21-28. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:gjpe&volume=4&issue=1&article=004>
- Kuter, F. Ö., & Kuter, M. (2012). Beden eğitimi ve spor yoluyla değerler eğitimi [Moral education through physical education and sports]. *Eğitim ve İnsani Bilimler Dergisi: Teori ve Uygulama*, 3(6), 75-94. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/eibd/issue/22679/242186>
- Lestari, P. I., & Prima, E. (2017). The implementation of traditional games to improve the social emotional early childhood. *Journal of Educational Science and Technology*, 3(3), 178-184. <https://doi.org/10.26858/est.v3i3.4212>
- Lestaringrum, A. (2017). The effects of traditional game 'congkak' and self-confidence towards logical mathematical intelligence of 5-6 years children. *Journal Ilmiah Pendidikan Prasekolah dan Sekolah Awal*, 3(1), 13-22. <https://doi.org/10.24269/jin.v3n1.2018.pp13-22>
- Lickona, T. (1992). *Educating form character how our school can teach respect and responsibility*. New York-Toronto-London-Sidney-Auckland: Bantam Books.

- Liu, W., Wang, J. & Xu, F. (2008). Middle school children's attitudes toward physical activity. *The ICHPER-SD Journal of Research International Council for Health, Physical Education, Recreation, Sport & Dance*, 3(2), 78-85.
- Lovat, T. (2011). Values education and holistic learning. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 50(3), 148-152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2011.07.007>
- Luna, P., Guerrero, J., & Cejudo, J. (2019). Improving adolescents' subjective well-being, trait emotional intelligence and social anxiety through a programme based on the sport education model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(10), 1821. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16101821>
- Ministry of National Education [MNE]. (2018). *Beden eğitimi ve spor dersi öğretim programı ortaokul 5, 6, 7. ve 8. sınıflar* [Physical education and sports lesson curriculum for middle school 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grades]. TTKB, Ankara. <http://mufredat.meb.gov.tr/ProgramDetay.aspx?PID=324>
- Mirzeoğlu, A. D. (2017). *Temel kavramlar. Model temelli beden eğitimi öğretimi* [Basic concept, Model-based physical education teaching]. 1st. Edition. (Editor: Mirzeoğlu, A. D.) Ankara: Spor Publishing House and Bookstore.
- Muñoz-Llerena, A., Núñez Pedrero, M., Flores-Aguilar, G., & López-Meneses, E. (2022). Design of a methodological intervention for developing respect, inclusion and equality in physical education. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 390. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010390>
- Özbal, A., Sağlam, M., & Cavkaytar, S. (2019). Implementing differentiated instruction approach in physical training and sports lesson. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 44(200), 291-312. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15390/EB.2019.8085>
- Özsarı, A., & Öztürk Çelik, D. (2021). Farklı okullarda eğitim gören öğrencilerin beden eğitimi ve spora ilişkin tutumları ile sosyal becerileri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi [Investigation of the relationship between the attitude towards physical education and sports and social skills of students studying in different schools]. *Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 4(2), 1-14. <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/comusbd/issue/64606/948121>
- Öztürk, Y. (2019). *Fiziksel etkinlik kartlarının 5. sınıf öğrencileri üzerindeki etkilerinin incelenmesi* [Examining the effects of physical activity cards on 5th grade students]. Unpublished Master Thesis. Marmara University Institute of Educational Sciences, İstanbul.
- Romanvican, M. G., Mundilarto, Supahar, & Istiyono, E. (2020). Development learning media based traditional games engklek for achievements mastery of the material and tolerance attitude. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 1440 012044. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1440/1/012044>
- Sağın, A. E., & Karabulut, Ö. (2019). Beden eğitimi ve spor dersine yönelik ortaokul öğrencilerinin değer düzeylerinin incelenmesi (Bağcılar ilçesi örneği) [Investigation of value levels of secondary school students for physical education and sport (Sample of bağcılar district)]. *International Journal of Mountaineering and Climbing*, 2(2), 27-34. <https://doi.org/10.36415/dagcilik.644204>
- Sertkahya, M., & Üren, H. (2021). İlköğretim 2. kademe ve ortaöğretim öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi dersine karşı tutumlarının çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi: Kemalpaşa ilçesi örneği [Examining the attitudes of primary, secondary and secondary school students towards physical education lesson in terms of various variables: The case of kemalpaşa]. *Uluslararası Güncel Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(1), 166-183. <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/intjces/issue/64208/839605>
- Sivrikaya, Ö., & Kılçık, M. (2017). İlköğretim okulları 2. kademe öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi ve spor dersine ilişkin tutumlarının belirlenmesi (Düzce örneği) [Determination of the secondary school students' attitudes with the course of physical education and sports (Düzce sample)]. *CBÜ Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 12(1), 1-15. <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/cbubesbd/issue/30403/327972>
- Subramaniam, P. R., & Silverman, S. (2007). Middle school students' attitudes toward physical education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 23(5), 602-611. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2007.02.003>
- Sümbüllü, Y. Z., & Altınışık, M. E. (2016). Geleneksel çocuk oyunlarının değerler eğitimi açısından önemi [The importance of traditional children's games in terms of values education]. *Erzurum Teknik Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 1(2), 73-85. <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/etusbed/issue/35461/393987>
- Syihabbudin, M., & Umami, K. N. (2020). Establishment of children's tolerance attitude with the traditional gobak sodor approach. *Pedagogik, Education, Islamic, Teaching, Learning*, 8(1), 260-291. <https://doi.org/10.33650/pjp.v8i1.1885>
- Taşdemir, N., Bayram, M., & Şam, C. T. (2021). Öğrencilerin beden eğitimi ve spor dersine yönelik tutumlarının çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi (Ağrı ili hamur ilçesi örneği) [A study of students' attitude towards physical training and sports lesson in terms of several variables (Examples from hamur, ağrı)]. *Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 23(4), 131-146. <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/ataunibesyo/issue/67477/1015485>
- Tavşancılı, E. (2018). *Tutumların ölçülmesi ve spss ile veri analizi* [Measuring attitudes and data analysis with spss]. 6th Edition. Ankara: Nobel Academic Publishing.
- Temel, A., & Kangalgil, M. (2021). Oyun ve fizikî etkinlikler dersi öğretim programı kazanımlarının gerçekleşmesine ilişkin sınıf öğretmenlerinin görüşleri [The opinions of primary school teachers about

- applying the achievements of teaching programme of the subject “game and physical activities”]. *Milli Eğitim Dergisi*, 50(229), 445-462. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/milliegitim/issue/60215/874865>
- Tepe, H. (2002). *Değerler ve değer bilgisi. Bilgi ve değer sempozyum bildirileri [Values and knowledge of value. Information and value symposium papers]*. (Editor: Yalçın, Y.). 1st Edition. Ankara: Vadi Publications.
- Wallhead, T. L., Garn, A. C., & Vidoni, C. (2013). Sport Education and social goals in physical education: Relationships with enjoyment, relatedness, and leisure-time physical activity. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 18(4), 427-441. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2012.690377>
- Yalız Solmaz, D., & Bayrak, C. (2016). Beden eğitimi dersindeki fiziksel etkinlik oyunlarının ilköğretim öğrencilerinin karakter gelişimleri üzerindeki etkisi [Affect on character development of elementary students of physical activity games within physical education lessons]. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 31(4), 644-656. <https://doi.org/10.16986/HUJE.2016015695>
- Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2018). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri [Qualitative research methods in the social sciences]*. 6th Edition. Ankara: Seçkin Publishing.
- Yıldız, R., & Kangalgil, M. (2021). Beden eğitimi ve spor öğretmenlerinin ilköğretim ikinci kademe beden eğitimi ve spor dersi kazanımlarının gerçekleştirilmesine ilişkin görüşleri [Views of physical education and sports teachers on primary education second stage physical education and sports course achievements]. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 18(40), 2146-2167. <https://doi.org/10.26466/opus.856590>
- Yıldız, R., & Özgül, F. (2017). Investigation of the effects of physical activity levels on sport behavior (fair-play) of the students participating in school sports at different branches (Sivas city example). *International Journal of Sports and Physical Education (IJSPE)*, 3(4), 40-46. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/2454-6380.0304007>
- Yılmaz, M. K., & Aytakin, R. İ. (2020). Genişletilmiş değer-tutum- davranış modeli bağlamında yeşil ürün satın alma davranışının incelenmesi [Investigation of green buying behavior in the context of an extended value-attitude-behavior model]. *Hitit Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 13(2), 439-465. <https://doi.org/10.17218/hititsosbil.786220>
- Zekioğlu, A., Gürsoy, S., Gürsoy, R., & Çamlıyer, H. (2020). Ortaokul öğrencilerinin beden eğitimi ve spor dersine yönelik tutumları ile öğrenmeye karşı sorumluluk davranışları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi [Investigation of the relationship between the attitudes of secondary school students towards physical education and sports class and responsibility behaviors towards learning]. *Humanistic Perspective*, 2(1), 9-17. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/hp/issue/52419/674214>